

BIASES AND (MIS-)REPRESENTATION OF FEMALE POLITICIANS IN NEWS MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

Research on gender bias in the media can also be closely related to news media exposure. Since the 1970s, researchers have worked to expose gender biases located within the mass media that make its appearance felt in various, innumerable ways. Female politicians get less exposure to the news than male politicians or are exposed negatively, thus preventing them from gaining public trust as political leaders (Sazali & Basit, 2020; Steiner, 2019). In contrast, the *Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action 1995* assigns the role of media a place in bringing greater attention to women's contributions as it aims to achieve equality across various fields. According to Djerf-Pierre & Edström (2020), voice and visibility in the news mass media have a significant influence in striving for gender equality and the elimination of stereotypes in society which are seen as a balance of composition, social roles, actions, perspectives, and the application of the principle of justice between men and women in society. The literature review method of qualitative evidence was chosen as a study design. This study aims to find out how to dismantle the discourse of news language in the concept of gender equality in mass media. This research offers the concept of Feminism Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis (FPDA), developed by British linguistic expert Judith Baxter (2018). The results of this study state that by using the FPDA as a method, researchers can deconstruct news scripts adapted to language classifications that lead to feminist discourse. Furthermore, in their deconstruction of such texts, researchers may further identify the agenda of media companies and their position on the feminism movement as a whole: whether they are anti-, pro-, or neutral to feminism and its objectives.

Keywords: gender, mass media, discourse, post-structural, feminism

INTRODUCTION

Gender bias has long been an exciting study among academics and has been a discussion topic in many circles outside of the academy. According to Johnson & Repta (2012), the discussion about different roles between men and women has been occurring since at least the 19th century. This multidimensional study further follows the debate about gender roles in sexuality, education, work, power, culture, knowledge, and other activities of production that exist between men and women.

The proliferation of the gender role phenomena is associated with the feminism movement, which aims to create equality between men and women across various social structures in society. The aim of the movement is to circumvent women being relegated to a kind of second-class human being after men, and thus, find their place as accepted, productive contributors in society's social strata (Huber, 2020; Mazur & McBride, 2023). In accordance with this development, the feminist movement not only struggles for equality between men and women but works too toward the empowerment of women themselves in social life. Structuralism perspective state that society plays a role in the formation of gender identity which creates gender identity, sexual, mental growth, acquisition of social roles, and gender preferences of each individual (Mousavi et al, 2019).

The political arena too is an exciting topic within the gender inequality discussion. Gender equality in politics has become a strategic issue to play in the promotion of women's interests. A political strategy to place women at the top of the leadership ranks will help women pursue policies that favor women. However, this strategy should also be supported by parties, potential candidates, and the voters' trust (Teele et al, 2018). Indeed, the more elected female politicians there are, the more women will be empowered, and gender equality programs achieved. Political academics have looked for factors that affect the minimal chances, or margins by which female politician's find themselves elected. One such study (Madsen, 2019) reveals that women have a perceived lack of public trust when it comes to politics due to low faith voters have in women as political candidates during an election cycle. Voters perceive female candidates as less capable, politically than those of their male counterparts. One reason for this (mis-)perception is the influence and amount of exposure to information conveyed in the form of news in the mass media, especially during the campaign period.

The lack of profile information on female political candidates through mass media coverage profoundly affects prospective voters' perceptions. Meanwhile, the influence of mass media exposure becomes significantly shaped too by writers' own perception and determinants of news content across mass media companies. The hierarchy theory of influence via media contents as authored by Pamela J. Shoemaker and Stephen D. Reese (Figure 1), and described by Krisdinanto (2017), highlights such issues.

Figure 1. Hierarchy of Influence by Pamela J. Shoemaker and Stephen D. Reese (Krisdinanto, 2017)

Krisdinanto (2017) shows, in accordance with Shoemaker and Reese, that media sometimes openly demonstrates their alignments or biases and as such play an active role in shaping social reality (p.9). One of the most basic influences is on media workers themselves as individuals, to the higher levels that encapsulate their routines, organization, and influences that lay outside the media; with ideological affects located on peripheries of these "spheres of influence" (see Figure 1). Through this, it can be determined that those who are able to control

the message of the mass media have the highest chance of winning an election (Tjung, Idris, & Idris, 2018).

Before an election moment, mass media provides exposure to political candidates through the news. This exposure occurs throughout the cycle of the campaign period according to government scheduling. During news coverage of political campaign events, voters decide whether or not to accept or reject political candidates who then compete for the final vote, including those women political candidates involved in the electoral process. In other words, news exposure that displays female figures through positive language, and shows support for females, increases the chances of women being elected through a gaining of public trust as facilitated through positive coverage. This argument is why research on gender and media that focuses on word choice and language (linguistics and discursive analysis) is significant as an effort in achieving equality for women who seek the opportunity to become leaders.

METHODS

The literature review method will be one way to collect and conclude some study results to find out where our study stands and gaps that can be used as new study opportunities in the future. It begins by collecting articles related to the same topic. Then it separates the articles as needed to find breaks in studies and define new studies to advance theory. A literature review can be used to stimulate new theories and make new statements and implications from the results of research practice. In the process, researchers chose research articles that discussed the gender gap in the politic, the influence of news exposure and gender issues, and the Feminism Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis (FPDA) concept which became the primary reading source that led to the concept of feminist discourse analysis research methods with a post-structuralism approach.

This literature study finds its place, primarily, in academics concerned with the study of mass media and gender. Many findings suggest that mass media's news exposure depicts women as weak figures whose position makes them incompatible with the role of leader (Adams, 2016; Brescoll, 2016; Eagly & Heilmann, 2016; Hoyt & Murphy, 2016). If a woman becomes a leader, so goes the thinking, it is more likely because they possess a different appearance than other women, or some other superficial determinant, as opposed to showing leadership qualities (Rudman, et al, 2012). It can be said that gender bias occurs in news exposures of female politicians who appear in news newspapers and television news about elections meanwhile political researchers believe that the more frequent and positive the news about political candidates, the greater the possibility of being elected and showing themselves as qualified politicians (Van der Pas & Aldering, 2020).

Female political candidates still need the mass media to display their profiles, as well as introduce themselves to potential voters in the election. Therefore, through their supporting political parties, female political candidates need to get support not only for political positions for female politicians but also for time and opportunities to communicate with the mass media (Miguel, 2008; Paxton et al, 2020). Unfortunately, journalists often appear more interested in the physical attractiveness of female political candidates alone, with mass media drawing upon these reductionist representations (and stereotypes) to frame female political candidates as different from male candidates in terms of competence. The media, focused only on female politicians' physical appearance, works to reduce positive exposure to their potential voting base.

Studies reveal that political fields rarely consider female political candidates. Accordingly, news exposure of female political candidates is not balanced when compared to male political candidates. Journalists tend to expose women to using a narrow, conventional gender frame by ignoring essential aspects of the campaign, such as the candidate's

background or their policy and strategy positions, not worthy of being leaders in the political field like men (Dolan et al. 2021). Therefore, very few women are seen to be elected and occupy positions within the political ranks of government (Baxter, 2018). As such, this literature study aims to determine whether the language of mass media news has a role to play in the exposure of women politicians during campaign periods and how to apply a Feminist Post-Structuralist Discourse Analysis (FPDA) methodology in news text research. In so doing, we show too how media companies show their alignment(s) with the feminist movement through textual exposure in the news media presentations.

This study aims to provide a repertoire of research methods on gender and media, especially with efforts to uncovering meaning(s) in news texts. With this research method in mind, the researcher will uncover what it sees as the real agenda of individual media companies: whether or not they have a supportive attitude toward the gender equality movement, and the empowerment of women, or instead remain neutral. This study is especially true of media companies in countries that adhere to more patriarchal systems.

Definitively, the patriarchal system emphasizes biological aspects between men and women. It is then concluded as a concept where men dominate, consider women second class, and take advantage of their weaknesses in various social practices (Khelghat-Doost & Sibly, 2020). They assume that men are naturally 'more equal' with physical and cognitive advantages best suited to roles of leadership. Conversely, women are portrayed through mass media as having characteristics of a 'maternalistic' nature, based primarily on motherhood, and as such are deemed unfit and unworthy of being leaders over men. It will be more appropriate if we are to believe the discourse, that women should involve themselves in domestic work alone. Accordingly, when viewed across the political realm, most participating parties prioritize male candidates in political competition over female candidates. Likewise, just as parties' support is lacking in championing female candidates, so too do we find similar attitudes among community groups who elect only male candidates.

GENDER EQUITY IN MASS MEDIA

The experience of the 2016 election in the United States between Donald Trump and Hillary Clinton is strong evidence that the basic principles of masculinity appear to be dominant in the political dynamics in the country. Researchers in the field of politics revealed that women lack equal representation in politics and the workspace; even men seem to be forced to show their dominance and power on the political stage (Schneider & Bos, 2019). In the political context of Asian countries, there are four factors that influence a female candidate's inability to secure political positions in the field. These factors include the influence of patriarchal culture as a power of influence over parties still dominated by men, media exposure control also by men, and lack of support across elements that could be fighting for women to take a more active role in politics (Nimrah & Sakaria, 2015; Misbahruddin, 2015).

In contrast, the equality movement, as it relates to mass media, has been greatly enhanced by its inclusion in the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (BPFA) 1995. Among 12 critical areas discussed at this conference, the media were still considered discriminatory to the female group. One of the main areas by which this takes place is the print and electronic media that creates – and perpetuates – stereotypes that strengthen men's dominance over the industry (Sadli, 2010). However, media in America, Europe, Africa, and Asia treat female politicians with a more negative frame than male politicians, for example, exposing aspects of gender and femininity, not on their abilities, competence in politics, vision, mission, and strength as politicians who deserve public attention., found media often defines women as closely related to what is perceived to be 'women's work' and as sexual objects of men. In addition, male dominance within these fields of media and television coverage, of both politician and layperson alike, also work to perpetuate stereotypes against women (Sazali & Basit, 2020).

Research since 1977s by academics in the field of journalism has proven that women get fewer mass media exposure than men and only deal with family, health, and education issues. Only a few get the opportunity as expert news sources. Even a few women take part in the mass media industry (Steiner, 2019). The symbolism that appears in the form of news texts and images presented by media are also heavily influenced by the dominance of male media workers. So much so, that whilst the impression of discrimination against women remains, conversely, it is downplayed as insignificant in the news (Li & Lei, 2010).

At times it appears that the primary source of every piece of information broadcast across the mass media is male-dominant. However, the latest study conducted in the UK states that the quantity of female journalists is not an obstacle in exposing gender gap issues in the news because they seem not to be a separate group and assimilate into the world of work professionally, but gender inequality in the media industry still arises (Krijnen & Van Bauwel, 2021). Likewise, in Iceland, the media is seen as gender-biased through its selection of only one woman from among four sources across all mass media platforms. However, although female mass mediaworkers have increased significantly (Jóhannsdóttir & Einarsdóttir, 2015), it is still a case that it is only women who repeatedly find themselves described as 'but only housewives', unable to make crucial decisions.

The practice of gender bias in mass media coverage and exposure also makes its appearance in several countries in the Asian region. The conclusions of several reviews validate that the mass media in Asia still hold strong biases in their reporting on women as news subjects compared to men (Vu et al, 2018; Kalra & Boukes, 2021, Ross, 2007). The mass media in Asia still see women only as news objects, worthy of being news sources, when they hold an attractive appearance which furthers stereotypes of the "bimbo" or in television broadcasting which presents women as decoration (Hariyanto, 2009). Furthermore, through these devices that (mis)represent women as sexual attractions, media exposure of this sort triggers men to act aggressively toward them in societal settings because of this sexual attractiveness that frames them as something for the taking.

Indeed, the equality between women's and men's roles in politics, when seen through this lens, as an issue that permeates all strata of society, furthers our understanding as to why, and how, the realms of politics remain masculine and remain complicated to achieve in Asia. A solid patriarchal culture helps perpetuate these beliefs and keeps women from having the opportunity to compete with men (Paxton et al, 2020; Purwanti, 2015; Hillman, 2018). Apart from the patriarchal culture that exists, the influence of religious doctrine and state hegemony too is dominated by men (Jati, 2014), making women a "second-class group" unable to find their place within politics. As such, it should come as no surprise that so few voters choose women as representatives when people, voters, are conditioned via media to trust only men as deserving of participation (Rhoads, 2012).

Through the news and mass media, broadcasting (i.e., exposure) can show their alignments by empowering women as a form of equality of the roles between women and men in politics. Academics in the field (Parawansa, 2002; Carter, 2003; Celis & Lovenduski, 2018) found that the mass media's role is essential in making women political candidates able to win their prospective voters' hearts. Indeed, news that is not neutral, lacks information and is not objective, triggers an emergence in public perception and opinions about whether a political candidate is even eligible to be elected or not as a people representative (Parawansa, 2002; Carter, 2003). This is why mass media exposure, in all its forms, is being considered, according to feminist activists, as a way to achieve the goal of equality between men and women in social spheres across society (Sharda, 2019) – and of course, the political field. To be sure, with gender equality in politics, the main objective is to maximize opportunities for alliances, participation, and policies that focus on women's interests (Celis & Lovenduski, 2018).

For feminists, the media is seen to play a significant role in fostering a gender-biased culture in society (Sharda, 2019). The media is still too focused on male figures as a news source over

women (Jenkins, 2002). Likewise, Wood (1994) states that the role (and perceptions) of players within the media industry itself dramatically influences the ways media presents women as a source of news. This perspective of masculinity controls the newsroom and is dominated by men as workers within the profession remains a factor overshadowing the nuances of news exposure, with the female figure as a source of the news forever misrepresented or left out.

According to the roles they play, women are getting less attention in everyday exposure through mass media (Collins, 2011). Instead, the exploitation of women's bodies becomes dominant across the mass media's news space (Byerly & Ross, 2008; Carter & Steiner, 2003). Likewise, during an election campaign, the exposure of female political candidates has not changed. Although most news coverage that does appear presents the vision and mission of female political candidates (Dewi, 2015), it is not uncommon to find coverage that still uses terms such as "beautiful candidate" in their presentation (Hillman, 2018). A linguistic device that further reinforces gender bias and an exploitation of their physical appearance.

According to Li & Lei (2010), mass media indirectly creates marginalization or attention toward women's voices through broadcast content. Therefore, the media has a powerful influence as a source of importance for prospective voters to determine which political candidates can become leaders and are eligible to be elected as representatives (Terkildsen and Schnell, 1997; Gidengil, 2007). One of the considerations is how the mass media displays political candidates' profiles through visual images. The way of dress, appearance, and narrative that surround a news subject, becomes news material, or points of reference which determine readers' perceptions (Hayes, Lawless & Baitinger, 2014).

FEMINISM POST-STRUCTURALISM DISCOURSE ANALYSIS AS A RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Previously, two French philosophers, Foucault (1972) and Derrida (1987), developed the theory of post-structuralism. The thought of this post-structuralist philosophical group was further developed toward identifying language as a location of power. That is, a way to assess, and critically analyze, "where power lies" (Foucault, 1972). The key to discovering the power inherent in language is to deconstruct the language itself to find the meaning(s) that are being conveyed (Garrity, 2010). Researchers focusing on feminist theories in the decades that followed, supported the arguments put forth by Foucault and Derrida, including Chris Weedon (1989).

Lastly, post-structuralist theory saw itself re-imagined by Judith Baxter in the year of 2013 as a way to examine power relations among males and females by tapping into the power that exists within language discourse; spoken as well as written. Baxter (2018) is the most recent research that examines language in mass media news coverage by using a discourse analysis method. The method, which Baxter (2003) called Feminism Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis (FPDA), as described in *Positioning Gender in Discourse: A Feminist Methodology* (2003), works as the key framework for this study. This theory emphasizes exposing the subject matter and discursive discourse found throughout news texts by using a feminist perspective. Previously, Baxter (2003) applied the same method to conversations between male and female groups among school students, as well as company management.

Through Post-structuralism theory and feminism, in collaboration with a research method in discourse analysis, Baxter (2003) was then able to create the research methodology Feminism Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis (FPDA). According to Baxter (2013), FPDA concepts deconstruct the dynamics of communicative interaction processes that involve women as subjects, and objects, of study by using a discourse approach. McCarthy, Matthiessen, & Slade (2010) suggest that discourse occurs through language, meaning, or ideas that appear through conversations, texts, and the language of everyday conversation. With this in mind, this investigation's primary key refers to the identity and relationship of objects to one another during the process of communicative interaction. According to Foucault (1972), the message

maker can also determine what position the object of communication will be in, whether strong or weak in its position.

In the early stages of an FPDA analysis, researchers can uncover whether, in a phenomenon, the communication process will place women as objects in a strong or weak position by paying attention to three influencing factors: power, knowledge, and discourse. This approach, closely associated with critical discourse (CD) and critical discourse analysis (CDA), combines a feminist post-structuralist approach to its investigation. This approach is reflective, as much as it is deconstructive, emphasizing the study of feminism across a range of criteria that does not stop at any one particular gender issue, but includes a variety of others (Shunderland, 2006) in its construction of a critical lens through which to view a problem.

Discourse analysis is a field of linguistic study that focuses on discourse, namely, the structure of a story that holds meaning and contains one or more ideas conveyed through verbal and non-verbal language. According to Hamad (Sahputra, 2021), discourse makes verbal and non-verbal language representations of reality as seen or experienced. Reality can be any situation, object, thought, person, event, or other phenomenon. Post-structuralist circles argue that all knowledge is discourse, including reality outside discourse because knowledge is a discursive product and reflective of actual reality (Newman, 2020).

The formation of discourse fostering is influenced by various cases, both intrinsically, in the form of views, ideas, and ideologies, and external influences such as the interests of other parties. This "coaching" then gives birth to the power of the discourse maker. The discourse forms the influence of the many factors behind that which is being said (or portrayed). It influences the choice of language, words, and facts that are being included or excluded, as well as the choice of methods or techniques used to convey its meaning to the public. Some meanings and images appear according to the main interests and objectives behind the discourse maker's way they convey the (ir) message. The objective of this study was to offer the concept of Feminism Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis (FPDA) as a research method to uncover news texts in the production of mass media.

FINDINGS

Discourse about women will always show the reality of the gap between men and women states Weedon (1989). Likewise, in gender studies in the mass media, the image of women, always marginalized when compared to men, is one of the primary sources of perception in social reality (Hardt & Rutter, 2004). Therefore, the study of gender-biased discourse in the mass media can be seen as widespread. There is no exception either when looking into the study of gender bias for women politicians (Adcock, 2010; Soza, 2014).

Reflecting on academic studies of post-structuralist feminism, such as those mentioned, the FPDA has several principles. Using FPDA can show that the emergence of context in social reality is highly dependent on language and reveals the background of the interacting subject. FPDA can even deconstruct the relationship between women and men when the interaction takes place and how it occurs. On top of this, FPDA, as a tool for analysis, also works to explain the assumptions and values resulting from the discourse analysis process.

The strength of FPDA is in its power to unearth discourse. Nevertheless, the objective of discursive studies, as pertains to this paper, is that it will understand the construction of the discourse and move away from the subjectivity of discourse itself (Motion, 1996). Researchers draw upon discursive approaches to determine material reality, one of which is language, which influences humans through "life processes" and other artefacts (Yardley, 2008). In her book *Positioning Gender in Discourse: A Feminist Methodology* (2003), Baxter states that there are several factors toward using FPDA theory as an approach and methodology. To be sure, discourse analysis that combines the study of Feminism with the paradigm of post-structuralism requires an interpretation of the apparent reality inherent within the discourse.

However, it can change according to the context that affects it.

Epistemologically, FPDA can dismantle the power transformation between men and women individually when interacting in specific contexts. There are times when the subject will be in a dominant state as an individual, but in others, the situation can be reversed. A dominant discourse will obtain discourse deconstruction that determines an individual's position, when it becomes strong or weak, within the overall context and reality of the communication that takes place. According to Butler's (1990) argument, CDA can be used to dismantle a post-structuralist discourse, because a dialectic of the relationship between conditions, materials, institutions, and social structures influences the discourse itself. Discourse interpretation can differ by using a different point of view, different goals and objectives, specific intentions, and what is confident because of the influence of power relations that influence interaction (Shunderland, 2006). Therefore, in post-structuralist circles, mass media is a relevant object of study using this methodological approach. It is because the process of creating discourse about women as news subjects make itself apparent through the power relations that take place in the language used (Baker, 2013).

The discursive reality also influences the language that occurs at this time. Especially in analyzing a text, the researcher must also understand the meaning of the discursive reality that occurs in order to understand the background of all that informs and shapes the manuscript. In examining news texts in the mass media, a collection of phrases, corpus, syntax, modalities, linguistic structures, and visible pronunciations appear. The first step to using this research method is to unpack the text's keywords, frequencies, collocations, and concordances. The text frequency will at least show the structure of the message, the theme that is the focus of the discussion, as well as patterns that take place across a text's construction. Before implementing the FPDA method, words and meanings appeared mixed. It can be a series of events, experiences, or discourses described in the language used. Later, in social relations, the nuances of gender, class, identification of subjects and objects, and even language, may change due to the ruling ideology prevalent at the time.

It is in this light that Baxter (2017) uses a post-structuralism approach because of the language used. Research can work to understand the implied meanings behind the mass media, whilst showing too their orientation toward issues of gender through articles mass media produce. Researchers need to uncover the true meaning of published news articles and the influence of power relations embedded within, which influence nuances of the resulting text. In his research, Baxter (2018) saw how the mass media positioned women as news subjects. The analysis method continues to deconstruct discourse through language characteristics and word choice used as a part of news content. The five features referred to are:

- (1) Names and nicknames,
- (2) Classification,
- (3) Identity,
- (4) Speech, and
- (5) Image.

Baxter's concepts align with classifications presented by Jenkins (2002) who issued 14 categories, which she calls "pen pix", to identify the categories of mass media publication manuscripts, and whether they show different treatment in presenting news between male and female politicians during the broadcast. According to Jenkins (2002), this category is motivated by women's political experience in Australia who feel mistreated and misrepresented by news coverage in the mass media. Throughout their careers as politicians, the mass media only reported on their appearance and clothes. Not only that, but the mass media in Australia also only reviewed information surrounding their roles as wives or homemakers and matters relating to their personal lives (Lee & Collins, 2009). In other words, female politicians feel they have a difference in the exposure of mass media coverage when

compared to that of male politicians.

Therefore, through these 14 categories, Jenkins (2002) divides her analysis/observations into private and public domains. The private sphere relates to a news source's personal life, including activities related to the family, both in the past and present. Meanwhile, the public sphere deals with relationships with people, organizations, and other activities outside the home and family. Jenkins (2002) 14 categories determine how news coverage shows support for women's activities, including public areas, such as education, social roles, politics, sports, and the military. Meanwhile, categories for private areas include spouse, children, family, physical appearance, completeness of appearance, personality, age, and background. In terms of numbers, the categories of public and private areas are not the same, as Jenkins (2002) concluded through broadcasts used to quantitatively describe news content. With news exposure displaying more women's news content in private areas of their lives, it can be argued, the media does not support the equality movement and the role(s) women have to play in public life. Conversely, news reports with more content about their public activities, showing the mass media supports the equality movement, along with the female contribution.

FPDA can be run as a methodology by first uploading words and sentences constructed through several of the classifications above, starting from language characters and 14 categories by Jenkins (2002). Sara Mills (1992) conveys that the methodology of discourse analysis through text can investigate the role of women as located throughout the news narrative. A meeting point will be obtained through the words and sentences in the news content and whether the female participant becomes the controlling (dominant and has power) or controlled party (depicted as weak and powerless). Mills (1992) sees how news events, such as those involving women in news texts, position them as subjects or objects at the subject-object level. Whether their presence has the power to present themselves or their thoughts, show their identity and independence, or whether their presence is only to complement a phenomenon of events, depends on others and is by no means more meaningful than items that include male parties. By looking comprehensively at all the components across an investigation, Baxter (2018) then classifies the attitudes and directions of mass media toward gender equality. A conclusion will emerge in which the mass media, the subject of this study, shows a pro-, neutral, or anti-feminist attitude. This classification by Baxter is called the Feminism Agenda Spectrum (FAS) (2018).

As a result of the analysis, mass media news articles can provide an accurate picture of women as subjects and news objects by introducing emerging linguistics, discursiveness, and even semiotics into the equation. Of the three attitudes that are shown in the conclusions of research results, FAS gives an overview as follows:

1. Pro-feminism:

This conclusion is motivated by Cameron's (2005) study, which revealed that pro-feminist media have similarities with the views of liberal Feminism. In her identification shows that pro-feminist mass media displays linguistic, discursive, and even semiotic features that show support for the existence of women as leaders. This movement is demonstrated by supporting voting rights and equality between male and female political candidates, just like the second wave of feminist groups.

2. Neutral:

In this classification, newspapers support the feminist movement but show differences in social and professional identification between men and women. Women appear to be given the same position as men within the social structure, but coverage still shows differences in women's roles. The language used in these news articles is also unclear as speech or actions aimed at showing open support for gender equality.

3. Anti-feminism:

identification in this group is located in the direction of a news script's content. The emphasis of this classification is that it is inappropriate for the female to be a leader. There is pressure from a patriarchal viewpoint, contending that women are not free, or able to make choices in carrying out functions as leaders.

Pro-feminism ← Neutral → Anti-feminism

To facilitate the application of the discourse analysis method using the FPDA approach, researchers look for the discursive context that appears in each news script. The following table facilitates analyzing news text discourse within an FPDA approach. According to the researcher, this table contains excerpts of news scripts with word choices or sentences containing context according to the characteristics of words and language that are the object of discourse research. After finding words and sentences that contain contexts that correspond to the language classification, it becomes easier for research to identify the findings of words and sentences to be analyzed in the next stage.

Table 1. The table of FPDA discourse analysis method

NEWS LANGUAGE CLASSIFICATION	WORDS AND SENTENCES IN THE NEWS	PUBLICATIO NDATE	NAME OF CANDIDATE	FEMINISM SPECTRUM AGENDA
This column is a place to put the language classification chosen by the researcher	Researchers enter words and sentence quotes that they feel meet the criteria according to the language classification object of research.	The date of publication of the newspaper containing the news	Contains the name of the female politician who is the subject of the news in the selected news script	The results of news discourse analysis will direct the tendency of news stories to show as anti-, neutral, or pro-feminist movement.

Likewise, Cathy Jenkins (2002) also mentions quantitative analysis with her 14 categories of pen pix. Accordingly, there will be a domination of either private or public sphere coverage shown over the course of a female politician's news exposure. The news content is considered neutral if there is a balance between the public and private news domains. If the dominant content in a news item relates to women's activities outside the home, it can be said that the media is pro-feminist. On the contrary, if news exposure is focused on more private issues, such as those mentioned above, it can be said the exposure is anti-feminist.

DISCUSSION

From all that has been presented, this researcher concludes that mass media is still gender-biased when comparing female news exposure to that of male coverage. Studies prove that the mass media, especially television, presents women with a less significant role than men

(Jenkins, 2002). Academics in media and gender also find that gender bias also applies to the political field. Studies show that female politicians do not have the same opportunities to exposure in the mass media as their male counterparts. Meanwhile, women need to get positions in politics so that their interests are fought for but need the support of parties, political candidates themselves and voters (Teele et al, 2018).

To complicate matters, female politicians need mass media as a place to introduce their vision and mission as political candidates and gain public trust as leaders. media sometimes openly demonstrates their alignments or biases, and as such play, an active role in shaping social reality (Krosdinanto, 2017) one of them is through exposure to the news presented. One such research method that can be used to examine how the mass media shows these biases in attitude toward supporting, or rejecting the feminist movement, is through discourse analysis, methods that can explore verbal and non-verbal meanings in the representation of reality seen and experienced (Sahputra, 2021).

Judith Baxter (2018) is an academician in language and linguistics who introduces Feminism Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis (FPDA) as a research methodology best suited to this course of critical examination. An FPDA research method allows researchers to choose language classifications according to the needs of their own research and deconstruct the manuscript according to the(ir) research objectives. Starting with determining what language classifications answer research objectives, and then deconstructing words and sentences in the news according to chosen language classifications, an FPDA approach brought research processes in line with a feminist spectrum, or agenda (Baxter, 2018).

The implication of this study is through the FPDA method, researchers are able to locate words and phraseology, along with the discourse (influences) that surround them, to demonstrate attitudes of the mass media when presenting news about politicians and leaders who are women. Ultimately, the FPDA research method can identify perspectives within the mass media, whether pro-, anti-, or neutral towards the Feminist movement, and how these perspectives serve as obstacles in pursuit of a Feminist objective such as equality. In addition to language classification, other classifications, such as the "pen pix" of Cathy Jenkins (2002), highlight mechanisms by which, over a specified period of news exposure, television news content utilises private and public areas of a female candidate's life that can then be analyzed to unearth companies' attitudes across news coverage.

It shows how the application of new research in regard to women politicians can be uncovered, and analyzed, using a discourse analysis methodology based on the FPDA approach. It is hoped that this article serves as the basis, and motivation, aimed at candidates for female leaders, political parties, or women's organizations to prepare them better to organize more positive language, attitudes, and speech to bring about more positive news exposure, whilst countering the biases and misrepresentations of female politicians in news media coverage and exposure by major networks.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

Theresia Diyah Wulandari was responsible for the data collection, analysis, and writing. Rani Ann Balaraman participated as a supervisor and revising the manuscript.

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